

Event-Triggered Output Feedback Stabilization of Networked Systems with External Disturbance

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Abstract—This paper addresses the problem of output feedback stabilization of continuous-time networked systems that are also perturbed by persistent external disturbances. An augmented state observer is designed in order to estimate both the state of the system and the external disturbance. Conditions for observability of the augmented system are provided based on the given system parameters. Stabilization of the output feedback networked system is achieved by means of event-triggered control strategies which reduce the number of feedback updates. A strictly positive lower-bound on the inter-event times is also provided which avoids Zeno behavior. Finally, this framework is extended to consider the existence of network induced delays. Similarly, conditions for stability and bounds on the inter-event times are presented.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN Networked Control Systems (NCS) a digital communication network is used to transfer information among control system components including actuators, controllers, and sensors [1]. The use of a shared communication channel for control systems may make feedback measurements inaccessible to the controller for long intervals of time. An approach followed by different authors is to keep the latest received feedback measurement constant until new information arrives from the controller, i.e. using a Zero-Order-Hold (ZOH), [2], [3].

The implementation of a model of the system in the controller node provides better performance in general since an estimate of the state of the system can be used for control during the time intervals that feedback measurements are not available. Model-based frameworks have been used by different authors for control of networked systems [4]-[9]. The work in [4]-[7] considers model uncertainties and no external disturbances while the authors of [8], [9] focus on attenuation of constant input disturbances by considering no plant-model mismatch. Similar model-based frameworks have been studied by different authors, [10]-[12].

In the present paper we use the state/disturbance observation approach presented in [13]. Here, we consider event-triggered strategies [14]-[17] for stabilization of open-loop unstable systems that are also subject to external and persistent disturbances and that transmit feedback updates through a limited bandwidth network. The results in the present paper address the case of disturbance rejection and consider the output feedback problem using state observers.

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Recent work has addressed the output feedback event-triggered control problem [9], [18]-[22]. The authors of [18] presented a comprehensive analysis based on impulsive system modeling of an output feedback system with external disturbance and with a dynamic controller. The approach in [9] used a state observer and a model-based approach to attenuate the effects of external disturbance.

In the present paper we implement an augmented state observer that provides estimates not only of the states of the disturbed system but also estimates of the unknown external disturbance. This augmented state observer is used in the networked system and we show that asymptotic stability can be achieved using event-based updates. This stability result is made possible by implementing a model-based framework that includes an estimate of the constant disturbance to compute the control input and by including an augmented observer system that asymptotically converges to the real state and disturbance. The use of the model-based approach and the augmented observer considerably improves the performance of the networked system compared to similar work in [8]-[9]. Additionally, we extend this work to consider piece-wise constant disturbances. Finally, this framework is used to address network induced delays which, with exception of [19], have not been studied in the context of output feedback event-triggered control.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the augmented state observer and provides observability conditions on the augmented system. Section III introduces the model-based architecture for control over networks. In Section IV we show asymptotic stability in the presence of constant disturbances using event-triggered techniques. Extensions to consider time delays are discussed in Section V. Examples are presented in Section VI and Section VII concludes the paper.

II. AUGMENTED STATE OBSERVER

This section describes the augmented state observer for joint estimation of plant states and input disturbances. Consider a dynamical system represented by

$$\dot{x}(t) = Ax(t) + B(u(t) + w(t)), \quad y(t) = Cx(t) \quad (1)$$

where $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $u(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$, and $y(t) \in \mathbb{R}^p$, represent the state, control input, and measurable output of the system, respectively. $w(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ represents the unknown constant external disturbance. It is assumed that the disturbance is bounded as follows $\|w(t)\| \leq W$. In this section we focus on state and disturbance estimation of (1). We design an augmented state observer under the assumption of continuous access to the input and output signals, $u(t)$ and $y(t)$ as in a traditional closed loop control system.

Fig. 1. Networked control system with external disturbance.
A: Actuator node. S: sensor node

The purpose of this augmented observer is to provide estimates not only of the state of the system $x(t)$ but also to obtain estimates of the unknown constant disturbance $w(t)$. Define the augmented state vector:

$$x_e(t) = \begin{bmatrix} x(t)^T & w(t)^T \end{bmatrix}^T. \quad (2)$$

The augmented system is given by:

$$\dot{x}_e(t) = A_e x_e(t) + B_e u(t), \quad y(t) = C_e x_e(t) \quad (3)$$

where

$$A_e = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad B_e = \begin{bmatrix} B \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad C_e = \begin{bmatrix} C & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

The following theorem provides conditions for observability of the augmented system. When the augmented system is observable it is possible to estimate both, the states and input disturbance of (1) and it is also possible to implement the augmented state observer in the networked configuration of Fig. 1 for control with limited communication.

Theorem 1. Assume the continuous-time pair (A, C) is observable, then (A_e, C_e) is observable if $\mathcal{N}(M) = \{0\}$, the nullspace of M contains only the zero vector, where

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ C & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

Proof. See [13] for proof.

The state observer is designed for the augmented system (4) and it is given by:

$$\dot{\bar{x}}_e(t) = (A_e - LC_e)\bar{x}_e(t) + B_e u(t) + Ly(t) \quad (6)$$

where L is a stabilizing observer gain for the augmented system, that is, the eigenvalues of $A_e - LC_e$ satisfy $\text{Re}(\lambda_i(A_e - LC_e)) < 0$ for $i=1, \dots, n+m$. This state observer will be used later, in Section IV and Section V, in the NCS represented in Fig. 1. Particular implementation details corresponding to the networked configuration as shown in Fig. 1 will be discussed in those sections.

III. MODEL-BASED NETWORKED ARCHITECTURE

The particular network configuration that we implement in this paper is the Model-Based Networked Control System (MB-NCS) architecture of [4]. The MB-NCS configuration makes use of an explicit model of the plant which is added to the actuator/controller node to compute the control input based on the state of the model rather than on the plant state. The state of the model is updated when the controller receives the measured state of the plant that is sent from the sensor node at time instants t_k .

Fig. 2. Model-based actuator/controller node.

The sensor is not co-located with the actuator/controller but feedback measurements are transmitted through a limited bandwidth communication network as shown in Fig. 1.

The system is perturbed by an external disturbance $w(t)$. Assume that the disturbance is a persistent disturbance; in particular, assume that it is a constant signal. This approach can be used in practice for piece-wise constant disturbances, but the system is not asymptotically stable since there is an infinite number of discrete changes on the disturbance as time goes to infinity. However, bounded stability can be obtained as it is shown in this paper.

IV. OUTPUT FEEDBACK EVENT-TRIGGERED CONTROL

The networked system in Fig. 1 contains a nominal model of the system in order to generate an estimate of the state of the disturbed system (1) and to compute the control input between update intervals. The actuator/controller node is shown in Fig. 2. Also note that (1) is open-loop unstable, in general. The model dynamics are given by:

$$\dot{\hat{x}}(t) = A\hat{x}(t) + B\hat{u}(t), \quad \hat{y}(t) = C\hat{x}(t). \quad (7)$$

where $\hat{u}(t) = K\hat{x}(t)$ is the model control input, where K is a stabilizing gain, that is, the eigenvalues of $A+BK$ (the closed-loop model) satisfy $\text{Re}(\lambda_i(A+BK)) < 0$ for $i=1, \dots, n$.

A. Constant disturbance.

The use of the augmented observer described in Section II provides an estimate of the unknown external disturbance that can be transmitted to the controller node in order to improve the control action by compensating for the effects of the disturbance $w(t)$, that is, the control input for the plant is given by

$$u(t) = K\hat{x}(t) - \hat{w}(t) \quad (8)$$

where $\hat{w}(t)$ represents the latest update of the disturbance estimate received at the controller node, that is,

$$\hat{w}(t) = \bar{w}(t_k) \quad \text{for } t \in [t_k, t_{k+1}) \quad (9)$$

where t_k represents the update time instants, for $k=1, 2, \dots$. In this work we implement event-triggered strategies to determine t_k . At the update instants the augmented observer state $\bar{x}_e(t_k)$ is received at the controller node. The observer state contains estimates of both, the states of the plant and the disturbance. The observed disturbance is kept constant in the controller node during the next update interval as described in (9) and the model state is updated using the part of the observer state corresponding to the estimated plant states, i.e.

Fig. 3. Model-based event-triggered control sensor node.

$$\hat{x}(t_k) = \bar{x}(t_k). \quad (10)$$

After a model update takes place the model keeps its normal execution as in (7).

The sensor node contains the augmented observer and it has continuous access to the output of the system $y(t)$. In order to provide the observer with the control input $u(t)$ copies of the model and the controller are implemented in the sensor node. This model copy is also updated using the observer state at the same time instants than the model in the controller, see Fig. 3. The purpose is to stabilize the system and reduce communication between the sensor and controller nodes.

Define the observer error

$$e(t) = x_e(t) - \bar{x}_e(t) \quad (11)$$

$$\dot{e}(t) = (A_e - LC_e)e(t). \quad (12)$$

Define also the model-state error:

$$\hat{e}(t) = x_e(t) - \begin{bmatrix} \hat{x}(t) \\ \hat{w}(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

$$\dot{\hat{e}}(t) = A_e \hat{e}(t) \quad \text{for } t \in [t_k, t_{k+1}). \quad (14)$$

The errors (11) and (13) cannot be measured since they depend on $x_e(t)$, that contains the system states and the external disturbance which are inaccessible. Finally, let us define the model-observer error

$$\bar{e}(t) = \bar{x}_e(t) - \begin{bmatrix} \hat{x}(t) \\ \hat{w}(t) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (15)$$

Note that this error can be computed and used to trigger events since $\bar{x}_e(t)$, $\hat{x}(t)$, and $\hat{w}(t)$ can be measured or computed. The dynamics of (15) can be expressed as

$$\dot{\bar{e}}(t) = A_e \bar{e}(t) + LC_e e(t) \quad \text{for } t \in [t_k, t_{k+1}). \quad (16)$$

The system/disturbance dynamics is given by

$$\dot{x}_e(t) = \begin{bmatrix} A+BK & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} x_e(t) + \begin{bmatrix} -BK & B \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \hat{e}(t) \quad (17)$$

where the dynamics of the system can be written simply as

$$\dot{x}(t) = (A+BK)x(t) + [-BK \ B] \hat{e}(t). \quad (18)$$

From (18) and using (11), (13), and (15) we have that

$$\dot{x}(t) = (A+BK)x(t) + [-BK \ B](e(t) + \bar{e}(t)). \quad (19)$$

Define the state $z(t) = [x(t)^T \ e(t)^T]^T$ so (12) and (19) can be written in compact form as follows

$$\dot{z}(t) = \Lambda z(t) + \Phi \bar{e} \quad (20)$$

where

$$\Lambda = \begin{bmatrix} A+BK & [-BK \ B] \\ 0 & A_e - LC_e \end{bmatrix}, \quad \Phi = \begin{bmatrix} [-BK \ B] \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (21)$$

Note that the eigenvalues of Λ are the eigenvalues of the stable matrices $A+BK$ and $A_e - LC_e$. Therefore, there exist $\beta, \lambda > 0$ such that the following holds

$$\|e^{\Lambda t}\| \leq \beta e^{-\lambda t}. \quad (22)$$

Theorem 2. The output feedback system described by (1) with event-based updates triggered when

$$\|\bar{e}(t)\| > \beta_u e^{-\lambda_u t} \quad (23)$$

is asymptotically stable for any constant disturbance $\|w(t)\| \leq W$ if (A,B) is stabilizable, (A,C) is observable and the nullspace of (5) contains only the zero vector, where $0 < \lambda_u < \lambda, \lambda_e$. Additionally the inter-event time intervals are lower bounded by

$$0 < \tau \leq t_{k+1} - t_k \quad (24)$$

where

$$\tau = \frac{1}{\|\Gamma\| + \lambda_u} \left((\lambda_e - \lambda_u)t_k + \ln \left(\frac{\beta_u}{\beta_e \|e_0\|} \right) \right) \quad (25)$$

when $\beta_u > \beta_e \|e_0\|$, where $\beta_e, \lambda_e > 0$ satisfy $\|e^{(A_e - LC_e)t}\| \leq \beta_e e^{-\lambda_e t}$, and

$$\Gamma = \begin{bmatrix} A_e & LC_e \\ 0 & A_e - LC_e \end{bmatrix}. \quad (26)$$

Proof. By implementing the threshold (23) we have that the model-observer error is reset to zero, $\bar{e}(t_k) = 0$, due to the updates (9)-(10) that occur at time t_k and the error satisfies $\|\bar{e}(t)\| \leq \beta_u e^{-\lambda_u t}$. Then, the response $z(t)$ satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} \|z(t)\| &\leq \beta e^{-\lambda t} \|z(0)\| + \int_0^t e^{\Lambda(t-s)} \|\Phi \bar{e}(s)\| ds \\ &\leq \beta e^{-\lambda t} \|z(0)\| + \beta \beta_u \|\Phi\| \int_0^t e^{-\lambda(t-s)} e^{-\lambda_u s} ds \\ &\leq \beta e^{-\lambda t} \|z(0)\| + \frac{\beta \beta_u \|\Phi\|}{\lambda - \lambda_u} (e^{-\lambda_u t} - e^{-\lambda t}) \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

where $\lambda - \lambda_u > 0$. Taking the limit as $t \rightarrow \infty$ we have

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \|z(t)\| \leq 0 \quad (28)$$

and the networked system is asymptotically stable.

In order to establish a lower-bound on the inter-event time intervals we write the model-observer error dynamics as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\bar{e}}(t) \\ \dot{e}(t) \end{bmatrix} = \Gamma \begin{bmatrix} \bar{e}(t) \\ e(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (29)$$

for $t \in [t_k, t_{k+1})$. Then, the following holds

$$\frac{d}{dt} \|\bar{e}(t)\| \leq \|\Gamma\| \left\| \begin{bmatrix} \bar{e}(t) \\ e(t) \end{bmatrix} \right\| \quad (30)$$

for $t \in [t_k, t_{k+1})$. Since $\bar{e}(t_k) = 0$, the growth of the model-observer error during the interval $t \in [t_k, t_{k+1})$ satisfies

$$\|\bar{e}(t - t_k)\| \leq e^{\|\Gamma\|(t-t_k)} \|e(t_k)\| \leq e^{\|\Gamma\|(t-t_k)} \beta_e e^{-\lambda_e t_k} \|e(0)\|. \quad (31)$$

It can be seen that the time it takes for $\bar{e}(t)$ to grow from zero to $\beta_u e^{-\lambda_u t}$ is equal or greater than the time it takes the last expression in (31) to reach the same value, then we can find the lower-bound on the inter-event time intervals by solving for $\tau = t - t_k$ in the following equation

$$e^{\|\Gamma\|\tau} \beta_e e^{-\lambda_e \tau} \|e(0)\| = \beta_u e^{-\lambda_u (\tau + t_k)} \quad (32)$$

to obtain (25) which is positive for any update time instant t_k according to the conditions imposed on the threshold parameters λ_u and β_u . ■

B. Piece-wise constant disturbance.

The combined model-based and state/disturbance estimation framework described in this paper can also be used in the case when the external disturbance is piece-wise constant. We define t_ω , $\omega=0,1,2,\dots$ as the time instants when the disturbance changes value. In order to obtain a bound on the state similar to (27) a lower bound on the difference $t_{\omega+1} - t_\omega$ will be required, that is, the disturbance will not change values very frequently; otherwise the observer will not be able to estimate a fast changing piece-wise constant disturbance.

In order to stabilize the system in the presence of abrupt changes on the disturbance we proceed as follows. When a change on the disturbance is detected the threshold (right-hand side of (23)) is reset to its initial value, that is, we use the threshold $\beta_u e^{-\lambda_u (t-t_\omega)}$ for $t \in [t_\omega, t_{\omega+1})$. In the following theorem we establish bounded stability and bounds on the inter-event time interval for the networked system (1) and we also determine the lower-bounds on the time intervals $t_{\omega+1} - t_\omega$ where these results hold.

Theorem 3. Assume that $\|x(0)\| \leq \chi$, the observer is initialized as $\bar{x}(0)=0, \bar{w}(0)=\bar{w}_0$, and the model is initialized as $\hat{x}(0)=0, \hat{w}(0)=\bar{w}_0$, where $\|\bar{w}_0\| \leq W$. Then, the state $x(t)$ of the system described by (1) with event-based updates triggered when

$$\|\bar{e}(t)\| > \beta_u e^{-\lambda_u (t-t_\omega)} \quad (33)$$

for $t \in [t_\omega, t_{\omega+1})$ is bounded by

$$\|x(t)\| \leq 2\beta(\chi+W)e^{-\lambda(t-t_\omega)} + \frac{\beta\beta_u\|\Phi\|}{\lambda-\lambda_u} (e^{-\lambda_u(t-t_\omega)} - e^{-\lambda(t-t_\omega)}) \quad (34)$$

for piece-wise constant disturbances that satisfy $\|w(t)\| \leq W$ and

$$t_{\omega+1} - t_\omega \geq \max\{\tau_{oz}, \tau_{oe}\} \quad (35)$$

if (A,B) is stabilizable, (A,C) is observable and the nullspace of (5) contains only the zero vector, where

$$\tau_{oe} = \frac{1}{\lambda_e} \ln\left(\frac{\beta_e(\chi+2W)}{\chi}\right). \text{ Also } \tau_{oz} = \frac{1}{\lambda_u} \ln\left(\frac{2\beta(\chi+W)}{\chi}\right) \text{ when}$$

$$2\beta(\chi+W) - \frac{\beta\beta_u\|\Phi\|}{\lambda-\lambda_u} > 0 \text{ and } \tau_{oz} = \frac{1}{\lambda_u} \ln\left(\frac{\beta\beta_u\|\Phi\|}{\chi(\lambda-\lambda_u)}\right) \text{ otherwise,}$$

where $0 < \lambda_u < \lambda, \lambda_e$. Additionally, the inter-event time

intervals during $t \in [t_\omega, t_{\omega+1})$ for $\omega=0,1,2,\dots$ are lower bounded by τ as in (24), where τ is now given by

$$\tau = \frac{1}{\|\Gamma\| + \lambda_u} \left((\lambda_e - \lambda_u)(t_k - t_\omega) + \ln\left(\frac{\beta_u}{\beta_e(\chi+2W)}\right) \right) \quad (36)$$

when $\beta_u > \beta_e(\chi+2W)$, where $\beta_e, \lambda_e > 0$ satisfy $\|e^{(A_e - LC_e)t}\| \leq \beta_e e^{-\lambda_e t}$.

Proof. First note that by the selection of initial conditions we have that $\|e(0)\| \leq \chi+2W$ and $\|x(0)\| \leq \|z(0)\| \leq 2(\chi+W)$. Then, by following the steps in (27) we have that

$$\|x(t)\| \leq \|z(t)\| \leq 2\beta(\chi+W)e^{-\lambda t} + \frac{\beta\beta_u\|\Phi\|}{\lambda-\lambda_u} (e^{-\lambda_u t} - e^{-\lambda t})$$

holds for $t \in [0, t_{\omega+1})$, for index $\omega=0$ (before the first change in the disturbance at time t_ω , $\omega=1$). In order to guarantee that a similar bound can be used after t_ω , $\omega=1$, we restrict the time instant t_ω to satisfy $\|x(t_\omega)\| \leq \chi$. This can be guaranteed by solving for t_ω in the following

$$2\beta(\chi+W)e^{-\lambda t_\omega} + \frac{\beta\beta_u\|\Phi\|}{\lambda-\lambda_u} (e^{-\lambda_u t_\omega} - e^{-\lambda t_\omega}) \leq \chi \quad (37)$$

which can be written as

$$e^{-\lambda_u t_\omega} \left(\frac{\beta\beta_u\|\Phi\|}{\lambda-\lambda_u} + \left(2\beta(\chi+W) - \frac{\beta\beta_u\|\Phi\|}{\lambda-\lambda_u} \right) e^{-(\lambda-\lambda_u)t_\omega} \right) \leq \chi. \quad (38)$$

We have that if $2\beta(\chi+W) - \frac{\beta\beta_u\|\Phi\|}{\lambda-\lambda_u} > 0$ the solution of

$$2\beta(\chi+W)e^{-\lambda_u t_\omega} \leq \chi \quad (39)$$

guarantees (37) since $\lambda - \lambda_u > 0$. Solving for t_ω in (39) we obtain $t_\omega \geq \frac{1}{\lambda_u} \ln\left(\frac{2\beta(\chi+W)}{\chi}\right)$. If $2\beta(\chi+W) - \frac{\beta\beta_u\|\Phi\|}{\lambda-\lambda_u} \leq 0$ then we can solve for t_ω in

$$\frac{\beta\beta_u\|\Phi\|}{\lambda-\lambda_u} e^{-\lambda_u t_\omega} \leq \chi \quad (40)$$

to obtain $t_\omega \geq \frac{1}{\lambda_u} \ln\left(\frac{\beta\beta_u\|\Phi\|}{\chi(\lambda-\lambda_u)}\right)$ which guarantees (37).

We also need to guarantee that $\|e(t_\omega)\| \leq \chi+2W$ which together with $\|x(t_\omega)\| \leq \chi$ ensures that $\|z(t_\omega)\| \leq 2(\chi+W)$. This can be accomplished as follows. The error at time t_ω changes abruptly since a change on the disturbance occurred at that particular time instant. The error at time t_ω can be described by

$$e(t_\omega) = e(t_\omega^-) - \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \bar{w}(t_\omega) \end{bmatrix} \quad (41)$$

where $\bar{w}(t_\omega) = w(t_\omega) - w(t_\omega^-)$ represents the variation of the disturbance at time t_ω . Then, we have that

$$\|e(t_\omega)\| \leq \|e(t_\omega^-)\| + 2W \leq \beta_e e^{-\lambda_e t} \|e(0)\| + 2W. \quad (42)$$

Similarly, let us solve for t_w in the following expression

$$\beta_e e^{-\lambda_e t_\omega} \|e(0)\| + 2W \leq \chi + 2W \quad (43)$$

which results in $t_\omega \geq \frac{1}{\lambda_e} \ln \left(\frac{\beta_e(\chi + 2W)}{\chi} \right)$.

Summarizing, we have that if t_ω , $\omega=1$, is such that (37) and (43) hold, then $\|x(t_\omega)\| \leq \chi$, $\|e(t_\omega)\| \leq \chi + 2W$, and $\|z(t_\omega)\| \leq 2(\chi + W)$, for $\omega=1$, which are the same expressions that bound the initial conditions. Then, by induction, we have that if (35) holds for all $\omega=0,1,2,\dots$ then the same conditions on the state and the observer error are true for any time instant t_ω , $\omega=0,1,2,\dots$ and the norm of the state satisfies the decreasing bound (34).

The lower-bound (36) can be obtained following similar steps as in the proof of Theorem 2. ■

V. OUTPUT FEEDBACK EVENT-TRIGGERED CONTROL WITH DELAYS

This section considers the case when known constant delays exist in the communication channel. The updates are sent by the sensor node at time t_k and they are received at the controller node at time $t_k + d$. We implement two models at the sensor node, labeled by $\hat{x}_s(t)$ and $\hat{x}_c(t)$. The model state $\hat{x}_s(t)$ is used to compute events and it is updated at the event times t_k using the current observer state, that is, $\hat{x}_s(t_k) = \bar{x}(t_k)$. The second model, $\hat{x}_c(t)$, is updated at the same time as the model in the controller node using a time propagated value, that is, $\hat{x}_c(t_k) = e^{(A+BK)d} \bar{x}(t_k)$. This is done in order to generate the same control input at both sides of the network so the state observer is able to estimate the state of the system and the external disturbance.

Note that for both model states, we implement an associated model of the disturbance $\hat{w}_s(t)$ and $\hat{w}_c(t)$, which are updated as follows $\hat{w}_s(t) = \bar{w}(t_k)$ for $t \in [t_k, t_{k+1})$ and $\hat{w}_c(t) = \hat{w}_s(t_k)$ for $t \in [t_k + d, t_{k+1} + d)$.

Define the model-observer errors corresponding to each model state described in the previous paragraph

$$\bar{e}_s(t) = \bar{x}_e(t) - \begin{bmatrix} \hat{x}_s(t) \\ \hat{w}_s(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (44)$$

$$\dot{\bar{e}}_s(t) = A_e \bar{e}_s(t) + LC_e e(t) + BK \tilde{x}(t) - B \tilde{w}(t) \quad (45)$$

for $t \in [t_k, t_{k+1})$ and

$$\bar{e}_c(t) = \bar{x}_e(t) - \begin{bmatrix} \hat{x}_c(t) \\ \hat{w}_c(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (46)$$

$$\dot{\bar{e}}_c(t) = A_e \bar{e}_c(t) + LC_e e(t) \quad (47)$$

for $t \in [t_k + d, t_{k+1} + d)$, where $\tilde{x}(t) = \hat{x}_c(t) - \hat{x}_s(t)$ and $\tilde{w}(t) = \hat{w}_c(t) - \hat{w}_s(t)$. Note that $\tilde{x}(t) = \tilde{w}(t) = 0$ for $t \in [t_k + d, t_{k+1})$. In the case of network delays the response of the system is given by

$$\dot{x}(t) = (A + BK)x(t) + [-BK \quad B](e(t) + \bar{e}_c(t)). \quad (48)$$

Theorem 4. The output feedback system described by (1) with network induced delays d and with event-based updates triggered when

$$\|\bar{e}_s(t)\| > \beta_u e^{-\lambda_u t} \quad (49)$$

is asymptotically stable for any constant disturbance $\|w(t)\| \leq W$ if (A, B) is stabilizable, (A, C) is observable and the nullspace of (5) contains only the zero vector, where $0 < \lambda_u < \lambda < \lambda_e$. Additionally the inter-event time intervals are lower bounded by

$$0 < d \leq t_{k+1} - t_k \quad (50)$$

for any delay d satisfying

$$e^{-\lambda_u d} - \frac{\beta_A \tilde{\beta} \bar{B}}{\lambda_A} (e^{\lambda_A d} - 1) > 0 \quad (51)$$

when β_u and λ_u are chosen such that $\lambda_u \leq 2\lambda_e$ and

$$\beta_u \geq \frac{\beta_A \beta_e \|LC_e\| \|e_0\| (e^{\lambda_A d} - e^{-\lambda_e d})}{(\lambda_A + \lambda_e) \left(e^{-\lambda_u d} - \frac{\beta_A \tilde{\beta} \bar{B}}{\lambda_A} (e^{\lambda_A d} - 1) \right)} \quad (52)$$

where $\bar{B} = \begin{bmatrix} BK & -B \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$, $\tilde{\beta} > 0$, the constants $\beta_e, \lambda_e > 0$ satisfy $\|e^{(A_e - LC_e)t}\| \leq \beta_e e^{-\lambda_e t}$, and $\beta_A, \lambda_A > 0$ satisfy $\|e^{A t}\| \leq \beta_A e^{\lambda_A t}$.

VI. EXAMPLES

Example 1 (piece-wise constant disturbance). Consider the following continuous-time system [9]

$$\dot{x}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} -1/10 & 1/10 \\ 1/12 & -1/8 \end{bmatrix} x(t) + \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} u(t) + \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} w(t)$$

$$y(t) = [0 \quad 0.5] x(t).$$

The initial conditions are $x(0) = [3 \quad 1]^T$. The initial conditions for the model, the augmented observer, and the disturbance estimate in the controller node are all equal to zero. The system's controller gain and augmented system's observer gain are $K = [-0.250 \quad -0.925]$, $L = [6.591 \quad 1.630 \quad 9.979]^T$.

The system is subject to a piece-wise constant disturbance with bounded magnitude $W=0.5$. From (35) the condition on the admissible disturbance time intervals $t_{\omega+1} - t_\omega$ is $\max\{\tau_{oz}, \tau_{oe}\} = 61.77$ sec. The threshold parameters are selected as $\beta_u = 15, \lambda_u = 0.09$. Fig. 4 shows the states of the system, the states of the observer, and the states of the model when the approach described in Section IV-B is used. Fig. 5 shows the norm of the system along with the update time instants generated by the event-based threshold (33). The bottom of the figure shows the disturbance $w(t)$.

Fig. 4. Response of the event-triggered control system with piece-wise constant disturbance. Solid lines represent plant states x , dotted lines represent observer states $\bar{x}$, and dashed lines represent model states $\hat{x}$

Fig. 5. Norm of the state for the event-triggered control system with piecewise constant disturbance where the dark arrows represent the update instants. The bottom plot shows the disturbance $w(t)$

Fig. 6. Response of the event-triggered control system with constant disturbance and delay. Solid lines represent plant states x , dotted lines represent observer states $\hat{x}$, and dashed lines represent the delayed model states $\hat{x}_c(t)$. The dark arrows at the bottom represent the update instants

Example 2 (delays). Consider the unstable system

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}(t) &= \begin{bmatrix} 0.14 & 0.42 \\ -0.36 & 0.10 \end{bmatrix} x(t) + \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 \\ 0.2 \end{bmatrix} u(t) + \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 \\ 0.2 \end{bmatrix} w(t) \\ y(t) &= \begin{bmatrix} 0.8 & -0.6 \end{bmatrix} x(t). \end{aligned}$$

The initial conditions are $x(0) = [0.8 \ 0.65]^T$ and the constant disturbance $w(t) = 0.3$. The delay is $d = 0.4$ sec, the threshold parameters are $\beta_u = 8.95$, $\lambda_u = 0.08$. The controller and observer gains are $K = [-0.062 \ -2.419]$, $L = [1.592 \ -0.011 \ 0.426]^T$.

Results of simulations are shown in Fig. 6 where it can be seen that the system is asymptotically stable and significant reduction of communication is obtained using event-triggered techniques in the presence of network delays.

VII. CONCLUSION

An event-triggered approach for networked systems perturbed by external disturbances was discussed in this paper. An augmented state observer was used in order to estimate both plant states and the external disturbance and a model-based event-triggered framework was implemented to compute the control inputs for the intervals of time that the networked system operates in open-loop. This approach was extended to consider network induced delays. Stability

results and exclusion of Zeno behavior were demonstrated for the no-delay and the delay cases.

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